

D6.6 Public Communication Materials

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020- NMBP-ST-IND-2019 – 862192
Project title	SunCoChem: Photoelectrocatalytic device for sun-driven CO ₂ conversion into green chemicals
Duration of the project	May 2020 – April 2024 (48 months)
WP/Task:	WP6 / T6.2. T6.4.
Document due Date:	30/04/2022
Actual date of delivery	22/04/2022
Leader of this deliverable	EUT
Document status	FINAL

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	07/04/2022	Míriam Vendrell (EUT)	First draft version
0.2	11/04/2022	Marina Presas (EUT)	Review 1 st draft version
0.3	12/04/2022	Míriam Vendrell (EUT)	Production of final version
0.4	12/04/2022	Freddy Liendo (HST)	Revision
0.4	13/04/2022	Míriam Vendrell (EUT)	Implementation of changes and production of final version

Executive summary

EUT is responsible for designing and implementing the SunCoChem communication strategy through its Research Communications Office, but all consortium partners are involved in it.

This deliverable details the communication materials that have been prepared from M1-M23 including, among others, the development of project's visual identity, the production of digital dissemination and promotional materials and project website, social media activity and press release written. An evaluation of media impacts, as well as social media statistics is included.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information sheet	1
Executive summary	2
Table of contents	2
List of figures	3
List of tables	5
List of abbreviations	5
Introduction.....	6
1. Communication materials	7
1.0 Project’s corporate visual identity.....	7
1.1 Public Website.....	9
1.1.0 Website analytics (M1 – M23).....	10
1.1.1 New pages created.....	11
1.2 Promotional materials	24
1.2.0 Info-sheet	24
1.2.1 Rollup	25
1.2.2 Trifold	25
1.2.3 Project general presentation	27
1.2.4 General poster.....	27
1.2.5 Poster layout.....	29
1.2.6 Audiovisual materials.....	30
1.2.7 Cluster promotional materials	32
1.3 Social Media	36
1.3.0 Twitter.....	36
1.3.1 LinkedIn.....	38
1.3.2 YouTube.....	40
1.3.3 Partners Channels.....	41
1.4 Media relations	43
1.5 Community of Interest.....	45
1.6 Partners communication activities.....	48
2. Communication KPIs	51
3. ANNEX	52
3.0 Articles published in media outlets.....	52
3.1 Communication actions carried out by partners	53

List of figures

Figure 1: SunCoChem Communication and Dissemination Channels / Activities	7
Figure 3: Black and White logo positive	7
Figure 5: SunCoChem logo with a colour background	8
Figure 2: Full Colour logo.....	7
Figure 4: Black and White logo negative	8
Figure 6: View of some pages of SunCoChem deliverable template	8
Figure 7: View of stationery materials	8
Figure 8: SunCoChem graphic resources	9
Figure 9: Current website structure	10
Figure 10: Visitor Map (left) and number of sessions per device type (right)	10
Figure 11: SunCoChem website menu with the “News & Events” section	11
Figure 12: View of “Project news” page	12
Figure 13: View of “Events participated” page.....	13
Figure 14: View of “SunCoChem webinar” page	14
Figure 15: View of the page dedicated to EU Green Week workshop organised.....	15
Figure 16: SunCoChem website menu with the “Results” section	15
Figure 17: View of “Media impacts” page.....	16
Figure 18: View of “Project Materials” page	18
Figure 19: View of “Audiovisual Materials” page	19
Figure 20: View of “Scientific production” page	20
Figure 21: View of part of the “Deliverables” page	21
Figure 22: View of the “Cluster projects” page	23
Figure 23: SunCoChem info-sheet.....	24
Figure 24: View of the two versions of SunCoChem rollup.....	25
Figure 25: SunCoChem trifold.....	26
Figure 26: View of SunCoChem power point general presentation	27
Figure 27: SunCoChem general poster.....	28
Figure 28: SunCoChem poster layout.....	29
Figure 29: View of the two SunCoChem videos produced	31
Figure 30: Road2GreenChem cluster logo.....	32
Figure 31: View of Road2GreenChem factsheet.....	33
Figure 32: Screenshot of the Road2GreenChem video.....	34
Figure 33: Pages of the Road2GreenChem manifesto.....	35
Figure 34: View of SunCoChem Twitter profile.....	36
Figure 35: Examples of tweets published on SunCoChem Twitter profile.....	37
Figure 36: SunCoChem LinkedIn profile	38
Figure 37: Examples of posts published on SunCoChem LinkedIn account.....	39
Figure 38: View of SunCoChem YouTube	40
Figure 39: Examples of partners’ posts about SunCoChem.....	42
Figure 40: Press release published on SunCoChem website. See the full text here.	43
Figure 41: Spanish press release published in the EUT webpage. See the full text here	44
Figure 42: Spanish press release published in DOW’s webpage. See the full text here	44
Figure 43: Community of Interest sign up form.....	46
Figure 44: Example of some banners created to promote the Community of Interest sign up form on social media.....	47
Figure 45: Inclusion of SunCoChem information on Eurecat’s website	48
Figure 46: Inclusion of SunCoChem information on Hysytech’s website	49

Figure 47: Inclusion of SunCoChem information on Laurentia's website 49
Figure 48: Inclusion of SunCoChem information on Avantium's website 50

List of tables

Table 1: SunCoChem Twitter Data Analytics (May 2020 – March 2022) 38
Table 2: SunCoChem LinkedIn Data Analytics (November 2021 – March 2022)..... 40
Table 3: Communication KPIs..... 51
Table 4: SunCoChem Media Clipping (M1- M23)..... 52
Table 5: Partners communication activities (M1- M23)..... 53

List of abbreviations

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>RIA</i>	<i>Research and Innovation Action</i>
<i>TPER</i>	<i>Tandem Photoelectrocatalytic Reactor</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporate Identity</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

SunCoChem in a nutshell:

SunCoChem is a **4-year Research and Innovation Action (RIA) project**, with the objective to develop a **competitive and modular self-biased tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactor (TPER) to efficiently produce oxo-products from CO₂, water and sunlight.**

By achieving this, SunCoChem addresses the need of the European Chemical Industry to reduce their dependence on carbon feedstock by producing highly competitive and integrated solutions enabling the carbon-neutral production of energy and high-value chemicals.

EUT is the partner leader of Task 6.4 Communication Activities, but all consortium partners are involved in it. Task 6.4 has the objective to create and provide all the communication materials needed for conveying the project to a broad group of users.

All the actions will consider EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication.

(https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm)

1. Communication materials

During the first two years of the project, EUT as the leader of Communication & Dissemination task produced and designed **different types of communication materials** and carried out **communication activities**. All these actions have the objective to disseminate the project and catch the attention of both the scientific community and the industrial community, as well as the non-specialised audience about the potential benefits and impact of the research done in SunCoChem.

The communication materials developed during this period (M1-M23) include the creation of SunCoChem's corporate visual identity, project's website and social media channels and the production of different promotional materials and a press release, among others.

Figure 1: SunCoChem Communication and Dissemination Channels / Activities

The following sections present and detail the main communication materials and tasks that have been done during the first two years of SunCoChem project by EUT with the collaboration of all the partners.

1.1 Project's corporate visual identity

According to the work plan, EUT developed SunCoChem's Visual Corporate Identity (VCI), aimed at **properly aligning all communication materials across all the project's tasks**.

The Visual Corporate Identity includes the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities and a visual identity standards' guidebook, which defines and outlines how to use identifying elements pertaining to SunCoChem, including the different uses of the logo, corporate colours, fonts, stationery and graphic resources.

For more information and details of the SunCoChem Visual Corporate Identity refer to **D6.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan**.

Figure 2: Full Colour logo

Figure 3: Black and White logo positive

Figure 4: Black and White logo negative

Figure 5: SunCoChem logo with a colour background

Figure 6: View of some pages of SunCoChem deliverable template

Figure 7: View of stationery materials

Figure 8: SunCoChem graphic resources

1.2 Public Website

The SunCoChem's project website (www.suncochem.eu) was launched in August 2020 (M3) by EUT, with the objective to serve as the main information channel for users interested in learning more about the project. The website displays the project's basic information, objectives, demonstrators and expected results.

Furthermore, the website is the **main anchor for all communication and dissemination activities related to the project and serves as a central point of entry for all public material**. The website is regularly updated with new information about SunCoChem, and conferences or exhibitions attended by the consortium.

SunCoChem's website follows the corporate visual identity of the project and gives access to its social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube).

Deliverable **D6.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan**, submitted in M3, summarises and details the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed, as well as the data protection measures adopted within the site.

Figure 9: Current website structure

1.2.1 Website analytics (M1 – M23)

The SunCoChem website has Matomo installed on the platform’s back-end to monitor all the traffic and obtain, every month, reports about the site’s performance. Since its launch in M3, the website has received **4,509 visits, 11,771 page visits, 3,298 users and 3,2 actions per visit**, including page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches per visit (*Data Analytics from August 2020 - M3 until March 31st, 2022- M23*).

As for **geographical and device traffic distribution, the majority of visits from M3-M23 have come from Spain** (denoting EUT’s own efforts disseminating it at the Spanish level). The picture seems relevant also to show that SunCoChem has impacted beyond European borders. Concerning devices, most of the sessions have been established through desktop devices.

Visitor Map

Figure 10: Visitor Map (left) and number of sessions per device type (right)

1.2.2 New pages created

From M1-M23, the SunCoChem's website has been updated with the publication of new sections to include specific information related project news, events attended and organised, project materials, audiovisual materials, etc.

1.2.2.1 News & Events

All the information related to project news or events organised and participated by the consortium is allocated in the section "News & Events", which is separated in the pages "Project News", "Events participated" and "Events organised", as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: SunCoChem website menu with the "News & Events" section

1.2.2.1.1 Project news

This section was created to allocate all the news related to SunCoChem project. Since its creation, **3 articles were published in this page**, including the first project's press release, information about a SunCoChem's survey to gather consumer companies' perceptions to adopt green oxo-chemicals, and an article encouraging to participate in a workshop organised within the EU Green Week.

PROJECT NEWS

[View all](#) [News](#) [Press releases](#)

The screenshot shows a webpage titled "PROJECT NEWS" with three news articles displayed in a grid. Each article includes a header image, a title, a date, a short text summary, and a "READ MORE" button.

- Article 1:**
 - Title:** "Towards Zero Pollution in the Production of Green Fuels and Chemicals"
 - Date:** News - May 23, 2021
 - Summary:** Join us for the EU Green Week workshop "Towards Zero Pollution in the Production of Green Fuels and Chemicals". The SunCoChem project invites you to participate in the webinar "Towards Zero Pollution in the Production of Green Fuels and Chemicals" with the objective to discuss how to use sunlight to manufacture fuels and chemicals from carbon...
 - Button:** READ MORE
- Article 2:**
 - Title:** "Help us gather consumer companies' perceptions and their willingness to adopt green oxo-chemicals in their products"
 - Date:** News - April 20, 2021
 - Summary:** Help us gather consumer companies' perceptions and their willingness to adopt green oxo-chemicals in their products. The SunCoChem project aims to address the need of the European Chemical Industry to reduce their dependence on carbon feedstock. Within the scope of the project, a solution based on a competitive tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactor will be developed. This...
 - Button:** READ MORE
- Article 3:**
 - Title:** "Chemical industry CO2 to be recovered to make new products"
 - Date:** Press releases - November 19, 2020
 - Summary:** Chemical industry CO2 to be recovered to make new products. The European SunCoChem project is to develop and provide the chemical industry with a sustainable alternative for producing chemicals using CO2 recovered from the industry itself together with the help of solar energy. The innovation involves designing a self-sufficient device for capturing and converting CO2...
 - Button:** READ MORE

Figure 12: View of "Project news" page

1.2.2.1.2 Participation in events

This page includes the articles about all the events participated by project partners and also an agenda showcasing the upcoming events planned.

From M1-M23, a total of **21 articles were published in this section** including information about fairs and exhibitions, project meetings, scientific conferences, workshops, summer schools and clustering events, among others.

PAST EVENTS

[View all](#)
[Clustering - Networking](#)
[Events](#)
[Fairs & Exhibitions](#)
[Open Calls](#)
[Project meetings](#)
[Scientific conferences](#)
[Summer Schools](#)
[Workshop](#)

The screenshot displays a grid of six event cards from the 'Events participated' page. Each card includes a representative image at the top, a title, a date, a category, a short description, and a 'READ MORE' button.

- Card 1:** Title: "Eurecat disseminates SunCoChem at the Advanced Factories Congress 2022". Date: "March 31, 2022". Category: "Fairs & Exhibitions".
- Card 2:** Title: "SunCoChem partners met online for their 18M meeting". Date: "November 10, 2021". Category: "Project meetings".
- Card 3:** Title: "SunCoChem presented during the IWA Odour and Air emissions Conference". Date: "October 27, 2021". Category: "Fairs & Exhibitions".
- Card 4:** Title: "Presentation of SunCoChem project during the Artificial Photosynthesis Summer School". Date: "October 23, 2021". Category: "Summer Schools".
- Card 5:** Title: "Partners from SunCoChem participate in the nanoGe Fall Meeting Online Conference". Date: "October 22, 2021". Category: "Scientific conferences".
- Card 6:** Title: "Eurecat presents SunCoChem project during the SusChem-España General Assembly". Date: "October 13, 2021". Category: "Clustering - Networking".

Figure 13: View of "Events participated" page

1.2.2.1.3 Organised events

This section is created to include all the information related to the events organised by SunCoChem project's partners. For now, the section is divided in **two specific pages related the SunCoChem webinar organised on April 2020 and the workshop organised within the EU Green Week in June 2020.**

SUNCOCHEM WEBINAR

Photocatalytic synthesis for a carbon-neutral production of fuels and chemicals

Webinar conference about **photo(electro)catalysis for a sustainable energy conversion** and storage into chemical bonds.

The webinar has comprised a session for better understanding of photo-electrochemical transformations driven by stable and efficient catalytic structures and how to combine photoelectrochemical measurements for their application in artificial photosynthesis. After a keynote session, **SunCoChem**, **FlowPhotoChem** and **DECADE** Horizon 2020 projects' concept and methodology have been presented.

April 28th – 15.00 – 17.00 CEST

Online

Targeted to:

- Undergraduate, graduate or PhD students willing to learn about photo(electro)catalytic synthesis
- Researchers in chemical technologies from Universities and research centers
- Professionals in the chemical industry (technicians, R&D managers), etc.

DOWNLOAD HERE SPEAKERS' PRESENTATIONS

SunCoChem webinar - Photocatalytic synthesis for a carbon-neutral production of fuels and chemicals

WEBINAR

Photocatalytic synthesis for a carbon neutral production of fuels and chemicals

Understanding the mechanism of (photo)electrochemical transformations in functional architectures for artificial photosynthesis

Francesca Maria Toma,
Chemical Sciences Division
Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
<https://www.tomaresearchgroup.org/>
fmtoma@lbl.gov

Berkeley Lab

#SunCoChem @SunCoChem_EU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Ver en YouTube

Figure 14: View of "SunCoChem webinar" page

Join us for the EU Green Week workshop “Towards Zero Pollution in the Production of Green Fuels and Chemicals”

SunCoChem project invites you to participate in the webinar “Towards Zero Pollution in the Production of Green Fuels and Chemicals” with the objective to discuss how to use sunlight to manufacture fuels and chemicals from carbon dioxide and water. The webinar will be organised as part of the **European Green Week** next Friday 4th of June.

Although the progress made in recent years in decreasing the pollution impact of the industrial sector across Europe, important challenges are still present in lowering the carbon footprint by progressively substituting the use of fossil fuels. For this reason, the European Commission is investing in disruptive technologies to develop negative emission solutions and lower Europe’s and industry’s carbon footprint.

During the webinar, attendants will examine which technologies are currently under development in Europe with the presentation of SunCoChem and 5 other related projects **FlowPhotoChem**, **Solar2Chem**, **Ocean Project**, **DECADE Project** and the **ReCode Project**, as well as the **SUNERGY** initiative.

Figure 15: View of the page dedicated to EU Green Week workshop organised

1.2.2.2 Results section

Furthermore, a **section dedicated to the project’s results and materials** was created, including specific pages for media impacts, deliverables, promotional and audiovisual materials and scientific production published by SunCoChem partners.

Figure 16: SunCoChem website menu with the “Results” section

1.2.2.2.1 Media impacts

This page was created around M7 (November 2020) when the first press release was produced and sent to partners’ media contacts. This section gives access to relevant articles featuring SunCoChem published in print and digital media at a local, national, and international level. For more information on articles published see section 1.5 Media

Relations. The section “Media impacts” will be continuously updated with more articles related to the project.

SUNCOCHEM IN THE NEWS

See below a selection of articles featuring SunCoChem:

November 23, 2021 | *Diari Més*
Solar, circular i col·laborativa: així serà la química (Catalan)

June 07, 2021 | *Interempresas*
El interés por el medio ambiente, motor de recuperación en todos los sectores económicos (Spanish)

March 29, 2021 | *Diari de Tarragona*
Los centros de investigación, la base (Catalan)

November 25, 2020 | *Residuos profesional*
El proyecto SunCoChem recuperará el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos (Spanish)

November 23, 2020 | *Retema – Revista Técnica de Medio Ambiente*
El proyecto SunCoChem permitirá recuperar el CO2 en plantas químicas para la generación de nuevos productos (Spanish)

November 20, 2020 | *Interempresas*
La Industria química recuperará el CO2 para generar nuevos productos (Spanish)

November 20, 2020 | *L'Econòmic – El Punt Avui*
Recuperar el CO2 de la indústria química per fer-ne nous productes (Catalan)

November 19, 2020 | *La Vanguardia*
Eurecat generará nuevos productos a partir del CO2 de la industria química (Spanish)

FULL CLIPPING STUDY:

Check the full clipping of the Suncochem project here:

Press releases

Chemical industry CO2 to be recovered to make new products
 Chemical industry CO2 to be recovered to make new products The European SunCoChem project is to develop and provide the chemical industry with a sustainable alternative for producing chemicals using CO2 recovered from the industry itself together with the help of solar energy. The innovation involves designing a self-sufficient device for capturing and converting CO2...
 November 19, 2020

Figure 17: View of “Media impacts” page

1.2.2.2.2 Project materials

This section was created around M8 (December 2020) once the project's promotional materials were validated and ready to be shared through all the communication channels.

The page also includes the different presentations and posters presented by partners in exhibitions, congresses, international conferences and other key events.

1.2.2.2.3 Audiovisual Materials

This section was created around May 2021 (M13) to include all the videos related SunCoChem project that were published on the YouTube account.

The page will be constantly updated as soon as new project's videos will be produced.

PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

<p>Factsheet</p> <p>PHOTOELECTROCATALYTIC DEVICE FOR SUN-DRIVEN CO₂ CONVERSION INTO GREEN CHEMICALS</p> <p>Solar energy Direct exploitation and utilization of solar energy</p> <p>Factsheet 1 file(s) 209.13 KB</p> <p>DOWNLOAD</p>	<p>Rollup</p> <p>PHOTOELECTROCATALYTIC DEVICE FOR SUN-DRIVEN CO₂ CONVERSION INTO GREEN CHEMICALS</p> <p>Rollup 1 file(s) 1.58 MB</p> <p>DOWNLOAD</p>
<p>Trifold</p> <p>Trifold 1 file(s) 1.44 MB</p> <p>DOWNLOAD</p>	<p>General presentation</p> <p>General presentation 1 file(s) 1.25 MB</p> <p>DOWNLOAD</p>

POSTERS

<p>Poster</p> <p>SunCO₂Chem Poster 1 file(s) 1.25 MB</p> <p>DOWNLOAD</p>	<p>"Carbon Dioxide Capture and Electrochemical Conversion with Ionic Liquids"</p> <p>(MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit – April 2021)</p> <p>Carbon Dioxide Capture and Electrochemical Conversion with Ionic Liquids 1 file(s) 1.13 MB</p> <p>DOWNLOAD</p>
---	--

PRESENTATIONS DELIVERED

<p>Electrocatalytic CO₂ Reduction on CuZnAl-Based Oxide Catalysts—Tuning of the H₂/CO Ratio</p> <p>(MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit – April 2021)</p> <p>Electrocatalytic CO₂ Reduction on CuZnAl-Based Oxide Catalysts—Tuning of the H₂/CO Ratio 1 file(s) 2.15 MB</p> <p>DOWNLOAD</p>	<p>Strategies for improving GDE Performance by a Uniform Dispersion of Catalyst Nanoparticles and an Optimal Nafion Content</p> <p>(MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit – April 2021)</p> <p>Strategies for improving GDE Performance by a Uniform Dispersion of Catalyst Nanoparticles and an Optimal Nafion Content 1 file(s) 1.03 MB</p> <p>DOWNLOAD</p>
<p>Facile and Scalable Synthesis of Cu₂O-SnO₂ Catalyst for the Photoelectrochemical CO₂ Conversion</p> <p>(MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit – April 2021)</p>	<p>Photo/electro catalytic cells for H₂ production and CO₂ valorisation</p> <p>(DENSYS online research forum – October 2020)</p>

Figure 18: View of “Project Materials” page

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

In this page you will be able to find all the videos related to SunCoChem project published in our Youtube channel

Figure 19: View of “Audiovisual Materials” page

1.2.2.2.4 Scientific production

This page was created to include all the scientific publications related to SunCoChem project published by partners and also a banner offering the link to the project’s [Zenodo Community](#) created.

1.2.2.2.5 Deliverables

This section, created at the beginning of the project, was recently updated with the publication of all the deliverables submitted. For the public deliverables we have included all the report, while for the confidential ones we have only published the executive summary.

SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

In this page you will be able to find the scientific publications related to SunCoChem project published by partners

Investigation of Gas Diffusion Electrode Systems for the Electrochemical CO₂ Conversion

Catalysts Journal, 2021

by Hilmar Guzmán, Federica Zammillo, Daniela Roldán, Camilla Galletti, Nunzio Russo and Simelys Hernández

ABSTRACT

Electrochemical CO₂ reduction is a promising carbon capture and utilisation technology. Herein, a continuous flow gas diffusion electrode (GDE)-cell configuration has been studied to convert CO₂ via electrochemical reduction under atmospheric conditions. To this purpose, Cu-based electrocatalysts immobilised on a porous and conductive GDE have been tested. Many system variables have been evaluated to find the most promising conditions able to lead to increased production of CO₂ reduction liquid products, specifically: applied potentials, catalyst loading, Nafion content, KHCO₃ electrolyte concentration, and the presence of metal oxides, like ZnO or/and Al₂O₃. In particular, the CO productivity increased at the lowest Nafion content of 15%, leading to syngas with an H₂/CO ratio of ~1. Meanwhile, at the highest Nafion content (45%), C₂+ products formation has been increased, and the CO selectivity has been decreased by 80%. The reported results revealed that the liquid crossover through the GDE highly impacts CO₂ diffusion to the catalyst active sites, thus reducing the CO₂ conversion efficiency. Through mathematical modelling, it has been confirmed that the increase of the local pH, coupled to the electrode-wetting, promotes the formation of bicarbonate species that deactivate the catalysts surface, hindering the mechanisms for the C₂+ liquid products generation. These results want to shine the spotlight on kinetics and transport limitations, shifting the focus from catalytic activity of materials to other involved factors

[Download paper](#)

Insights on the surface chemistry of BiVO₄ photoelectrodes and the role of Al overlayers on its water oxidation activity

Applied Catalysis A: General

by Kristine Rodulfo Tolod, Tapish Saboo, Simelys Hernández, Hilmar Guzmán, Micaela Castellino, Rowshanak Irani, Peter Bogdanoff, Fatwa F. Abdi, Elsjé Alessandra Quadrelli, Nunzio Russo.

ABSTRACT

Bismuth vanadate (BiVO₄) has surface states that give rise to defect levels that mediate electron-hole recombination. In order to minimize the inefficiencies, an ultrathin Al overlayer was deposited on the BiVO₄ electrodes. A 54 % improvement on the photocurrent density was obtained using the Al-modified BiVO₄ electrode, accompanied by a 15 % increase in stability over 7.5 h of continuous irradiation. Moreover, surface capacitance measurements showed that the Al overlayer was indeed passivating the surface states. We also shed light on the deposition of an Al overlayer on the surface of BiVO₄, by investigating the process on model BiVO₄ powders. This study presents useful, previously unreported information about the surface chemistry of BiVO₄ based on experimental methods and gives unique insights on the characterization of the BiVO₄ surface. The existence of surface reactive sites on BiVO₄ was confirmed and quantified (1.5 reactive sites/nm²) via chemical titration.

[Download paper](#)

FIND ALL SUNCOCHEM - RELATED RESEARCH
IN ZENODO OPEN-ACCESS REPOSITORY

[ACCESS ZENODO](#)

Figure 20: View of “Scientific production” page

PROJECT DELIVERABLES

WP1 – Development of Photo-Electrochemical Cell Materials

D1.1 Hybrid PEcats concept and performance specifications – Executive Summary
[DOWNLOAD](#)

1 file(s) 192 KB

D1.2 – Preliminary selection of the anode and cathode PEcats composition – Executive Summary
[DOWNLOAD](#)

1 file(s) 183.64 KB

> **D1.3** - Synthesis of the selected anode and cathode hybrid multifunctional PEcats for TRL3 cell optimization

D1.4 Scale up process for PEcats synthesis – Executive Summary
[DOWNLOAD](#)

1 file(s) 178.44 KB

> **D1.5** - Optimum photo-electrodes selected and report on the performance

WP2 – Development of Proton Transport, CO₂ Capture and Concentration Cell Materials

D2.1 – TBM and the CO₂ capture and concentration stage concept and specifications – Executive Summary
[DOWNLOAD](#)

1 file(s) 0.00 KB

D2.2 – Preliminary selection of materials for CO₂ capture and concentration stage and TBM – Executive Summary
[DOWNLOAD](#)

1 file(s) 186.37 KB

D2.3 – Synthesis of the selected polysulfone based membrane and novel ILs – Executive Summary
[DOWNLOAD](#)

1 file(s) 181.62 KB

D2.4 – Synthesis of the selected transparent bipolar membrane – Executive Summary
[DOWNLOAD](#)

1 file(s) 258.09 KB

> **D2.5** - Optimum membranes and ILs for CO₂ capture and concentration including scale-up strategy

> **D2.6** - Optimum Transparent Bipolar Membrane

Figure 21: View of part of the “Deliverables” page

1.2.2.3 Cluster projects

Finally, a new section to include all the **information related SunCoChem participation in the Road2GreenChem European Cluster** was created. This section explains the main objectives of the cluster and a brief introduction to the projects participating in it.

The section also includes the different promotional materials designed to promote and disseminate the cluster and its projects through different communication channels and key conferences and other events.

Road2GreenChem Cluster

The **SunCoChem project** is part of the **Road2GreenChem Cluster**, which brings together EU-funded R&D projects on **sustainable chemistry** with the objective to develop innovative technologies in the field of greener chemistry, solar energy and greener power, as a concrete alternative to the use of carbon feedstock in the European chemical industry, which is one of the main challenges of the *"European Green Deal"* strategy.

The projects participating in this cluster will boost awareness regarding the research results and promote knowledge transfer with relevant stakeholders, such as industry and academia, contributing to a safe and sustainable chemistry and increasing the protection of human health and the environment against hazardous chemicals.

The Road2GreenChem Cluster is formed by **FlowPhotoChem**, **ReCode**, **DECADE project**, **Solar2Chem**, **Ocean project** and **SunCoChem**.

Cluster materials

Road2GreenChem Cluster Manifesto 1 file(s) 7.47 MB	DOWNLOAD
Road2GreenChem Factsheet 1 file(s) 7.47 MB	DOWNLOAD

CLUSTER OBJECTIVES

- ✓ Achieving an efficient, scalable and sustainable high-value chemical production
- ✓ Contributing to meet the zero net carbon emissions targets fixed by the European Commission
- ✓ Technologies validated in real industrial environments
- ✓ Engaging with industrial and academic stakeholders, as well as policy makers to showcase the advantages of a solar-driven chemical industry in Europe
- ✓ Explore synergies between cluster projects for common dissemination and organisation of projects events on specific sustainable chemistry topics
- ✓ Maximising dissemination via joining efforts to prepare publications in journals and magazines

CLUSTER PROJECTS

Solar2Chem

Solar2Chem project has the objective to train 15 early-stage researchers to fill the existing gap in the European industrial landscape in the area of solar chemicals production and usage in technical, economic and policy aspect.

www.solar2chem.eu

FlowPhotoChem

This project aims to make high-value chemical production efficient, scalable and sustainable by adopting a modular photo(electric) catalytic reactor design. FlowPhotoChem advances the state-of-the-art in solar concentrators, membranes, catalysts and computational modelling to use solar energy, water and CO₂ to produce ethylene as a proof-of-concept.

www.flowphotochem.eu

DECADE

DECADE is developing an integrated photo-electrocatalytic (PEC) device for the distributed production of chemicals and fuels from CO₂, H₂O and solar energy as a key element for the transition to a low-carbon sustainable economic development. www.decadeproject.eu

ReCode

The ReCode project aims at developing an energy efficient technology to recover CO₂ from cement-production flue gases by the use of ionic liquids. A circular-economy-approach is enabled within the project: the CO₂ produced by cement manufacturing is re-used in a significant part within the plant itself to produce better cement-related products entailing less energy intensity.

www.recodeh2020.eu

OCEAN

OCEAN is a four-year project focused on the development of an integrated process for the production of high-value C₂ chemicals from carbon dioxide by using electrochemistry. Within the project, a new electrocatalysis will be compared with chemocatalysis for the production of high-value products, made out of the reduction products of CO₂.

www.spire2030.eu/ocean

Figure 22: View of the “Cluster projects” page

1.3 Promotional materials

SunCoChem counts with a set of different promotional materials including an **info-sheet**, **rollup**, **trifold**, a **general poster**, a **project's general presentation** and a **poster layout**.

All materials follow the project visual identity guidelines and are available to all the consortium in an electronic format, so they can be used every time a partner carries out a disseminating activity, such as attending to key conferences and fairs. The flyer, info-sheet, general poster, general presentation and rollup can be also found on the SunCoChem website (<https://suncochem.eu/promotional-materials/>). Promotional materials will be regularly updated based on partners' dissemination needs and project's developments.

1.3.1 Info-sheet

An A-4 info-sheet, based on the main objectives of the project, the technology and its expected results, was produced as a promotional material and published on the project's website.

The info-sheet features the SunCo2Chem logo at the top. The main title is "PHOTOELECTROCATALYTIC DEVICE FOR SUN-DRIVEN CO₂ CONVERSION INTO GREEN CHEMICALS". The text describes the project's aim to provide an alternative to produce oxo-chemicals without using raw materials derived from carbon oil, and details the technology of a tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactor. It also lists key objectives: Solar energy (Direct exploitation and utilization of solar energy), Circular economy (Revalorisation of industrial waste streams and by-products), Sustainable chemistry (Improved chemical energy conversion efficiency), and CO₂ conversion (Energy saving and CO₂ emissions reduction). A banner states: "SunCoChem addresses the need of the European Chemical Industry to reduce their dependence on carbon feedstock". The bottom section lists the consortium members (eurecat, Dow, HZB, DLR, ifit, amalium, iff, HYSYTECH, SOLARONIX, UNE) and contact information for Maria Navarro, Project Coordinator at Eurecat, Spain. It also includes the website (www.suncochem.eu), social media handles (@SunCoChem_EU, info@suncochem.eu), and a small European Union logo with a note: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 86202".

Figure 23: SunCoChem info-sheet

1.3.2 Rollup

Two different versions of a project rollup have been produced to be used when attending to dissemination events and/or to share through SunCoChem’s communication channels.

Figure 24: View of the two versions of SunCoChem rollup

1.3.3 Trifold

A trifold describing SunCoChem project was elaborated during the first months and shared to all consortium.

This document contains an introduction to the project, the main objectives, key outputs, the photoelectrocatalytic tandem reactor, and general information related to solar-driven chemistry and the European chemical industry.

ADDRESSING THE NEED OF THE EU CHEMICAL INDUSTRY TO REDUCE THEIR DEPENDENCE ON CARBON FEEDSTOCK

SunCoChem project aims to provide the chemical industry with an alternative to produce oxo-chemicals without using raw materials derived from fossil fuels.

The project is developing a solution based on a competitive tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactor to efficiently produce oxo-products from renewable energies based on CO₂, H₂O and solar energy.

This will be achieved by process intensification coupling a solar-driven carbon dioxide reduction to CO/water oxidation to O₂ with C-C bond carbonylation reaction catalysed by novel multifunctional hybrid photoelectrocatalysts.

Our goal is to provide a sustainable alternative for the production of traditionally fossil-based chemicals by using sunlight as an energy source and reusing CO₂ as a raw material in a circular economy approach

SunCO₂Chem

More information:
www.suncochem.eu
 @SunCoChem_EU
 info@suncochem.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 842792

Partners: eureka!, Dow, HZB, ifit, ifff, HYFYTECH, SOLARONEC, UNE, GFS, etc.

PHOTOELECTROCATALYTIC DEVICE FOR SUN-DRIVEN CO₂ CONVERSION INTO GREEN CHEMICALS

Carbon-neutral production of energy and high-value chemicals

PHOTOELECTROCATALYTIC TANDEM REACTOR

A competitive and modular self-biased photoelectrocatalytic tandem reactor

SunCoChem will offer an efficient system for producing high-value chemicals from CO₂, currently limited due to low CO₂ reactivity.

The photoelectrocatalytic tandem reactor will be validated in an industrial plant environment for the conversion of CO₂ emissions to produce different added-value chemicals.

THE PROCESS

- CO₂ capture from air/exhaust gases from the Chemical Industry and its selective concentration in Ionic Liquids
- Photocatalytic water oxidation (anode reaction)
- Photo-electrocatalytic CO₂ conversion to CO and H₂ (cathode reaction)
- C-C bond formation by in situ CO-carbonylation to oxo-products

PROJECT CONCEPT

The SunCoChem concept is based on Solar-driven chemistry.

SunCoChem project aims at exploiting a tandem photoelectrochemical CO₂ conversion route to produce CO as a key intermediate for the in-situ CO-carbonylation of chemicals to produce three important oxo-products of the chemical industry:

- Limonal™, by carbonylation of limonene
- Valeraldehyde, by carbonylation of Butene
- Glycolic Acid, by carbonylation of formaldehyde

SOLAR-DRIVEN CHEMISTRY

Solar-driven Chemistry refers to a future scenario for chemicals production based on the substitution of fossil feed-stocks as energy source and raw materials.

In a broader perspective, Solar-driven Chemistry is crucial for an already started transition to a new economic cycle in chemistry/energy production.

THE EUROPEAN CHEMICAL INDUSTRY

The European Chemical Industry strongly depends on carbon feedstock imports for energy and chemical manufacturing processes.

The introduction of sustainable chemistry using renewable resources to exploit CO₂ for the production of chemical products is an opportunity to an efficient use of resources and preservation of the environment.

30 Gt of CO₂ emitted yearly

95% Chemicals based on fossil fuels

Figure 25: SunCoChem trifold

1.3.4 Project general presentation

In order to support the communication of the SunCoChem project, a power point presentation was prepared. Each partner is able to add new slides and complete the presentation according to their needs and to the event to be attended and/or audience.

The general presentation designed provides a general overview about the project, its main objectives, the project's phases, key outputs, expected benefits and general information related the European Chemical Industry and the solar-driven chemistry.

Figure 26: View of SunCoChem power point general presentation

1.3.5 General poster

An A-0 poster was designed to be shared through communication channels and presented in different conferences, exhibitions, fairs or other events in which partners are going to participate.

The poster includes general information about the project, the technology, the concept and the main results to be achieved.

Addressing the needs of the European Chemical Industry for a carbon-neutral production of energy and high-value chemicals

SunCoChem project aims to provide the chemical industry with an alternative to produce oxo-products without using raw materials derived from fossil fuels.

The project is developing a solution based on a competitive tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactor to efficiently produce oxo-products from renewable energies based on CO₂, H₂O and solar energy.

This will be achieved by process intensification coupling a solar-driven carbon dioxide reduction to CO/ water oxidation to O₂ with C-C bond carbonylation reaction catalysed by novel multifunctional hybrid photoelectrocatalysts.

PROJECT CONCEPT

SunCoChem project exploits a tandem photoelectrochemical CO₂ conversion route to produce CO as a key intermediate for the in-situ CO-carbonylation of chemicals to produce three important oxo-products of the chemical industry.

A competitive and modular self-biased photoelectrocatalytic tandem reactor.

SunCoChem will offer an efficient system for producing high-value chemicals from CO₂, currently limited due to low CO₂ reactivity. The reactor will be validated in an industrial plant environment for the conversion of CO₂ emissions to produce three oxo-chemicals based on the use of CO₂ as a renewable carbon source: Glycolic Acid, Valeraldehyde and LimonicTM.

Our goal is to provide a sustainable alternative for the production of traditionally fossil-based chemicals by using sunlight as an energy source and reusing CO₂ as a raw material in a circular economy approach.

Consortium:

Contact us:

Miriam Diaz de los Bernardos
Eurecat's Chemical Technology Unit
miriam.diaz@eurecat.org

www.suncochem.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862192

Figure 27: SunCoChem general poster

1.3.6 Poster layout

A poster layout was designed to be used and adapted by all partners when need it. The document includes guidelines on how to structure the content and information along the poster.

Figure 28: SunCoChem poster layout

1.3.7 Audiovisual materials

On the other hand, to communicate SunCoChem project and its results **several videos** are planned. For now, **2 videos** were produced, which have been published in the YouTube project channel.

- “Politecnico di Torino presents SunCoChem in the European Researchers’ Night”. A short video regarding the participation of SunCoChem partners during the European Researchers Night celebrated in Torino (Italy). September 2021.
- “SunCoChem webinar – Photoelectrocatalytic synthesis for a carbon-neutral production of fuels and chemicals”. Video of the webinar organised by the project and celebrated last May 2021.

These videos, which have achieved more than 100 visualisations, have been published also in SunCoChem’s website and shared through the project’s social media.

Polito presents SunCoChem in the European Researchers' Night

SunCoChem webinar - Photocatalytic synthesis for a carbon-neutral production of fuels and chemicals

Figure 29: View of the two SunCoChem videos produced

1.3.8 Cluster promotional materials

Within the Road2GreenChem cluster, in which SunCoChem is participating as *detailed in D6.4 First Plan of Use and Dissemination of Results*, several promotional materials have been designed to be used in dissemination activities and generate awareness about the cluster and its sustainable chemistry projects.

For more details about the cluster promotional materials you can refer to ***D6.4 First Plan of Use and Dissemination of Results***.

1.3.8.1 Cluster visual corporate identity

The visual identity of the Road2GreenChem cluster has also been created, in collaboration with the Horizon Results Booster, including the main corporate colours, typography and logos.

Figure 30: Road2GreenChem cluster logo

1.3.8.2 Cluster factsheet

A factsheet with general information about the Road2GreenChem cluster was created including information about the cluster, its main objectives, expected results and the six European projects participating in it.

The factsheet was produced in the context of the Horizon Results Booster and with the collaboration of all the projects forming the cluster.

ROAD 2 GREEN CHEM

Path towards safe & sustainable chemicals through renewable energy

Chemicals are essential in our modern society. They are used in many sectors, like health, energy, mobility and housing.

However, the chemical industry is among the biggest sources of emissions within the industrial sector.

In order to reach the goals set by the EU Green Deal, the industry's transformation is key.

The Cluster

In line with this objective, the Road2GreenChem Cluster aims to develop innovative technologies for green chemistry, solar energy and green power to cut out the use of carbon feedstock in the chemical industry.

Road2GreenChem will provide:

- Competitive technologies allowing the production of chemicals through sustainable energies and methods, like solar energy and CO₂ recycling, in a circular economy perspective;
- a new generation of scientists with broad multidisciplinary and multisectoral skills.

The group aims to achieve:

- Efficient, scalable and sustainable high-value chemical production;
- Validation of technologies in real industrial environments;
- A realistic comparison of the current technologies with the actual fossil-fuel-based approach from the perspective of the technoeconomic, environmental, societal and market future impacts.

Discover Road2GreenChem's innovation and take part to the green revolution.

This factsheet has been produced by ICONS in the context of the Horizon Results Boosterservices delivered to SOLARCHEM (GA N. 861703), FlowPhotoChem (GA N. 862453), SunCoChem (GA N. 862192), RECODE (GA N. 768583), DECADE (GA N. 862030) and OCEAN (GA N. 767798). This product does not reflect the views of the European Commission.
horizonresultsbooster.eu

Figure 31: View of Road2GreenChem factsheet

1.3.8.3 Cluster promotional video

A video explaining the main objectives of the project, its benefits, the projects participating in it, and the expected results was produced. This video has been shared through all the communication channels of the project and will be used for any dissemination activity trying to promote the SunCoChem participation in this cluster. You can see the Road2GreenChem video [here](#).

Figure 32: Screenshot of the Road2GreenChem video

1.3.8.4 Joint manifesto

A joint manifesto was created including the general information of the cluster and the 6 European projects participating in it, as well as the main commitments and the contact details for each project. The manifesto is already included in SunCoChem website and has been shared through all the other communication channels.

MANIFESTO

Developing the future paths towards safe & sustainable chemicals

The Road2GreenChem Cluster

We are six EU-funded projects developing and demonstrating innovative technologies for green chemistry, solar energy and green power to ultimately defossilise the chemical industry through closure of the carbon cycle. Our technologies will help Europe meet the ambitious climate targets of the EU Green Deal and contribute to achieving UN Sustainable Development Goals.

The group is addressing the growing need for:

- Secure, clean and efficient energy,
- Climate and environmental action, resource efficiency and sustainable raw materials,
- Clean and green production of chemicals without fossil fuels,
- New chemicals and materials safe and sustainable by design, from cradle to grave.

DECADE - A novel approach to photoelectrocatalytic devices.
www.decadeproject.eu

FlowPhotoChem - Developing a modular flow technology for solar chemistry.
www.flowphotochem.eu

OCEAN - New C2 paths in electrochemical conversion of CO₂ at demo scale.
www.aspire2050.eu/ocean

RECODE - Recycling carbon dioxide from the cement industry to produce added-value additives.
www.recodeh2020.eu

Solar2Chem - Training the next generation of solar chemical scientists and engineers.
www.solar2chem.eu

SunCoChem - Developing a photoelectrocatalytic tandem reactor to manufacture chemical products from renewable energies.
www.suncochem.eu

We, the representatives of the Road2GreenChem Cluster acknowledge that:

- Chemicals are essential in our modern society but the chemical industry is among the biggest sources of emissions within the industrial sector.
- In order to reach the ambitious climate goals set by the EU Green Deal, disruptive technologies to transform the chemicals industry are key.
- Real world demonstrations of the transformative potential of green chemistry, solar energy and green power for the chemicals industry are essential to drive uptake, scale-up and further innovation in the future.

There we declare our commitment to:

- Engage with academic, industrial and policy stakeholders to showcase the advantages of a solar-driven chemical industry in Europe,
- Highlight the green production of chemical products and drive a move away from fossil fuels in chemicals manufacturing,
- Develop and demonstrate innovative technologies in real-world settings to support wider uptake,
- Establish new standards for chemical industry defossilisation.

We sign this Manifesto on February 15th, 2022

 Dr. Pau Farràs Project Coordinator info@solar2chem.eu	 Prof. Simelys Hernández Project Scientific Coordinator info@recodeh2020.eu	 Maria Navarro Project Coordinator info@suncochem.eu
 Dr. Pau Farràs Project Coordinator info@flowphotochem.eu	 Prof. Siglinda Perathoner Project Coordinator perathon@unime.it	 Prof. Gabriele Centi Project Coordinator centi@unime.it

Discover Road2GreenChem's innovation and take part in the green revolution.

This manifesto has been produced by ICONIS in the context of the Horizon Results Boosters services delivered to SOLAR2CHEM (GA N. 861151), FlowPhotoChem (GA N. 862453), SunCoChem (GA N. 862192), RECODE (GA N. 768583), DECADE (GA N. 862030) and OCEAN (GA N. 767799). This product does not reflect the views of the European Commission.

Figure 33: Pages of the Road2GreenChem manifesto

1.4 Social Media

EUT is managing SunCoChem social media accounts, including a Twitter profile ([@SunCoChem EU](#)) created at M1, a [LinkedIn profile](#) (created at M19) and a [YouTube channel](#) (created at M12).

Partners contribute to spreading the word through their corporate and personal Social Media channels, including accounts on Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook or Instagram.

The project coordinator is responsible for notify the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels.

For more details about Social Media strategy and activity please refer to **D6.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan**.

1.4.1 Twitter

Twitter, in SunCoChem project, aims to serve as a channel to communicate about the project development to European institutions, academia and the industry, engage with members of identified stakeholder groups and promote the use of social media complicities between SunCoChem and its sister projects, such as FlowPhotoChem, DECODE, Recode, Ocean and Solar2Chem, among others.

Figure 34: View of SunCoChem Twitter profile

EUT creates monthly a content plan with different types of publications to be disseminated through SunCoChem Twitter account. In addition, all partners can propose new content to be distributed though this channel.

The different posts published included: content curation with news and information related to project's topics, events in which partners have participated, dissemination of consortium meetings, promotion of the community of interests sign-up form, distribution of promotional materials, the press release produced, promotion of the events organised and news about SunCoChem and Road2GreenChem cluster, among others.

SunCoChem H2020 Project @SunCoChem_EU · Jan 21

#SunCoChem is the first project at developing a self-biased photo-reactor to efficiently produce oxo-products from #CO2, water and #sunlight

More information

suncochem.eu
SunCoChem project - An alternative route for oxo-products production
SunCoChem project aims to provide the chemical industry with an alternative to produce oxo-chemicals without using raw materials.

SunCoChem H2020 Project @SunCoChem_EU · May 26, 2021

#SunCoChem will be showcased at @Eurecat_news booth during the 2021 @greenweek as a key project working on the production of #SustainableChemicals towards a zero-pollution ambition.

Get in touch with us during the virtual exhibition to find out more!

SunCoChem H2020 Project @SunCoChem_EU · Jun 22, 2021

Find out more about #SunCoChem project addressing the needs of the EU #ChemicalIndustry for carbon-neutral production of #energy and high-value #chemicals.

Subscribe now! cutt.ly/ikm1BUm

SunCoChem H2020 Project @SunCoChem_EU · Jun 2, 2021

[#SunCoChem #research] Answer our survey and help us to explore experts' perceptions and willingness to adopt a carbon-neutral green technology for #oxoproducts production

Answer the survey!

docs.google.com
Green oxo-products: experts' perceptions and ado...
Title: Green oxo-products: experts' perceptions and adoption willingness in consumer packaged goods ...

SunCoChem H2020 Project @SunCoChem_EU · Feb 21

Learn more about Road2GreenChem cluster, comprised by #SunCoChem, @flowphotochem, @DECADEproject, @Ocean_h2020, @solar2chem, @RecodeH2020 working on #sustainablechemistry

youtube.com
Road2GreenChem European Cluster - Path toward...
The SunCoChem project is part of the Road2GreenChem Cluster, which brings together ...

13 18

Figure 35: Examples of tweets published on SunCoChem Twitter profile

At M23 (March 2022), the SunCoChem Twitter account counts with **354 followers** and **has generated 377 tweets and more than 198K impressions**.

Table 1: SunCoChem Twitter Data Analytics (May 2020 – March 2022)

SunCoChem Twitter Account	M23	Target by the end of the project
Followers	354	100
Total Tweets	377	200
Impressions	198,747	50,000
Likes on Tweets	832	100
Retweets	338	30
Mentions	118	20

1.4.2 LinkedIn

On the other hand, **LinkedIn** is a platform for the interaction among professionals to exchange experiences to improve their work placement. SunCoChem account on LinkedIn, created at M19 (November 2021), allows project partners to connect with the industrial and academic community, as well as connect and engage with sustainable chemistry, solar energy and renewable energies stakeholders. Following the social media guidelines, the publication pace in LinkedIn is less frequent than Twitter. Content is based on project news, events organised and participated, and reports and publications produced in the framework of the project or by trusted sources.

Figure 36: SunCoChem LinkedIn profile

SunCoChem
82 seguidores
1 mes • Editado •

Currently, the European **#ChemicalIndustry** is strongly depending on carbon feedstock imports for energy and chemical manufacturing processes, which are based over 95% on the use of fossil fuels. To solve these challenges, **#SunCoChem** **#sustainablechemistry** project provides the chemical industry with a sustainable alternative to efficiently produce high-value chemicals without using raw materials derived from carbon or oil.

<https://suncochem.eu/>

Ver traducción

SunCoChem
82 seguidores
2 días •

#SunCoChem project is part of the **#Road2GreenChem** Cluster, which brings together EU-funded R&D projects on **#sustainablechemistry** with the objective to develop innovative technologies in the field of **green chemistry**, solar energy and greener power, as a concrete alternative to the use of carbon feedstock in the European chemical industry. With this initiative, projects participating are working together to maximise the impact of their research results related to sustainable chemistry and carbon capture technologies, among others. The cluster is also formed by **FlowPhotoChem**, **Solar2Chem** Project, **DECADE** project, **Ocean** Project and **RECODEH2020**.

<https://lnkd.in/dwQHzrJr>

Ver traducción

Cluster projects - SunCoChem

SunCoChem
82 seguidores
1 mes • Editado •

The **#SunCoChem** project addresses the need of the European **#ChemicalIndustry** to reduce their dependence on carbon feedstock by producing highly competitive and integrated solutions enabling the carbon-neutral production of **#energy** and high-value chemicals. Subscribe now to our community of interest and be informed about our latest news and upcoming events!

The project is coordinated by **Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Catalunya** and participated by **Hysytech s.r.l.**, **Avantium International Flavors & Fragrances**, **International Hellenic University**, **Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin**, **IoLTec Ionic Liquids Technologies GmbH**, **Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia**, **Politecnico di Torino**, **Centre national de la recherche scientifique**, **Solaronix**, **UNE**, **Asociación Española de Normalización** and **Laurentia Technologies**

https://lnkd.in/ewrW_ZqI

Ver traducción

SunCoChem
82 seguidores
3 meses •

#SunCoChem addresses the needs of the EU **#ChemicalIndustry** for carbon-neutral production of **#energy** and high-value chemicals by developing and validating a photoelectrocatalytic reactor to produce oxo-products from **#CO2** and sunlight energy

The project goal is to provide an alternative for the production of traditionally fossil-based **#chemicals** by using **#sunlight** as an **#energy** source and reusing **#CO2emissions** from the **#ChemicalIndustry** **#CircularEconomy**

Coordinated by **Eurecat - Technology Centre of Catalonia** and participated by **Hysytech s.r.l.**, **International Flavors & Fragrances**, **Dow**, **Avantium**, **Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin**, **International Hellenic University**, **IoLTec Ionic Liquids Technologies GmbH**, **Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia**, **Politecnico di Torino**, **Centre national de la recherche scientifique**, **Solaronix**, **UNE** - **Asociación Española de Normalización**, **Laurentia Technologies**.

<https://suncochem.eu>

Ver traducción

Figure 37: Examples of posts published on SunCoChem LinkedIn account

At M23 (March 2022), the SunCoChem LinkedIn account counts with **94 followers** and has generated **25 tweets** and more than **7K impressions**.

Table 2: SunCoChem LinkedIn Data Analytics (November 2021 – March 2022)

SunCoChem LinkedIn profile	M22	Target by the end of the project
Followers	94	150
Total posts	25	50
Impressions	7,663	10,000
Likes/Reactions	39	100

1.4.3 YouTube

Finally, **YouTube** has been mainly used as a repository of videos and allocates all videos produced by partners during the project, which are also disseminated through the Social Media channels and the project website. Until M23, **3 videos** have been published in SunCoChem YouTube including the video related SunCoChem webinar celebrated in April 2021, the participation of POLITO in the European Researchers Night and the Road2GreenChem Cluster video.

Figure 38: View of SunCoChem YouTube

At M23 (March 2022), the SunCoChem YouTube channel account counts with **3 subscribers, 3 videos and more than 140 views.**

1.4.4 Partners Channels

Partners also shared SunCoChem news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook, mainly), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published on SunCoChem's website or on Social Media accounts.

Just summing the activity in partners' corporate social media accounts, mentioned at section 3.1.4.3 Partners Channels of the D6.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, from M1-M22, partners have posted a total of **56 posts in their corporate social media accounts, accumulating 219 likes and 48 shares/retweets.**

Eurecat @Eurecat_news · Nov 23, 2020

A Eurecat coordinem @SunCoChem_EU, que desenvoluparà un reactor per fabricar productes químics a partir d'energies renovables basades en el diòxid de carboni (CO2) recuperat de la mateixa indústria química i amb l'ajuda d'energia solar

#QuímicaSostenible
bit.ly/3m9rYYQ

DISAT Ingegneria Chimica PoliTo
 46 seguidors
 3 horas · Editado

If you are interested to keep updated about the #future #technologies that will substitute fossil-fuel-based feedstocks and energy in the chemical industry.. Subscribe to the [SunCoChem](#) newsletter !

#H2020 Project of CREST - Catalytic Reaction Engineering for Sustainable Technologies at DISAT Dipartimento di Scienza Applicata e Tecnologia (Department of Applied Science and Technology)

Ver traducción

SunCoChem
 70 seguidors
 3 horas · Editado

The innovation behind #SunCoChem involves the design of a self-sufficient device for capturing and converting #CO2 in a single unit. The system will cut costs, lower CO2 emissions and enhance solar energy conversion efficiency for producing chemicals without using fossil fuels. Subscribe to our community of interests to learn more about the project, our main results, latest news and upcoming events!

Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Catalunya Hysytech s.r.l. Avantium Dow IoLTec Ionic Liquids Technologies GmbH Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin International Flavors & Fragrances Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia Laurentia Technologies CNRS Politecnico di Torino Solaronix UNE Asociación Española de Normalización International Hellenic University Maria Navarro Miriam Díaz de los Bernardos Laura Armayones Carranza Hilmar Guzmán Simelys Hernández Alessia Fortunati Sergio Bocchini Mariajose López Tendero

https://lnkd.in/ewfW_Zqi

Ver traducción

Dow Tarragona @DowTarragona

En 2020 entramos a formar parte del proyecto europeo @SunCoChem_EU. Su objetivo es el desarrollo de un reactor tándem fotoelectrocatalítico para fabricar productos químicos a partir de #EnergíasRenovables basadas en CO2, agua y luz solar.

buff.ly/3jyJem
 Translate Tweet

SunCoChem aborda la necesidad de la industria química europea de reducir su dependencia de la materia prima de carbono mediante la generación de soluciones integradas y altamente competitivas que permitan la producción de energía y productos químicos de alto valor sin emisiones de carbono. De esta forma, pretende proporcionar una alternativa para producir oxo-químicos sin hacer uso de materias primas derivadas del carbono o petróleo.

Más información en www.dow.es y www.suncochem.eu

UNE Asociación Española de Normalización @Normas... · May 5

Participamos en la reunión inicial del proyecto @EU_H2020 #SUNCOCHEM. Desarrollará un reactor fotoelectrocatalítico para producir eficientemente productos basados en oxígeno a partir de CO2, agua y luz solar.

#StandardsforInnovation #EstándaresUNE

You Retweeted

Hysytech Srl @hysytech · 2h

Read our latest updates about the #projects @SunCoChem_EU and @RecodeH2020, both aimed at the conversion of the waste #CO2 from industrial flue #gases.

#research #innovation #engineering #greenchemistry #UEH2020 #H2020

1 3

Figure 39: Examples of partners' posts about SunCoChem

1.5 Media relations

During M1-M23, SunCoChem Communication and Dissemination leader EUT, produced **1 press release** with general information about the project and its consortium which was **distributed to all partners and adapted to several languages**.

EUT wrote the first press release with the inputs of all the project's partners, which validated all the content before sending it to the media outlets. Additionally, EUT identified, and will be continuously identifying, general and specialised media contacts to send the press release and spread the word about the project to society in general.

The press release produced had an important impact on online and print media. As a result, SunCoChem project has been featured in **28 media general and specialised media outlets at regional, national and international level**, including La Vanguardia, InterEmpresas Industria Química, Revista PQ, RETEMA, Diari de Tarragona and Izaro – Manufacturing Technology, among others. *See Annex 3.1 for a complete list of articles featuring SunCoChem.*

- **Consortium press release:** [Chemical industry CO₂ to be recovered to make new products](#)

Chemical industry CO₂ to be recovered to make new products

- The European SunCoChem project is to develop and provide the chemical industry with a sustainable alternative for producing chemicals using CO₂ recovered from the industry itself together with the help of solar energy.
- The innovation involves designing a self-sufficient device for capturing and converting CO₂ in a single unit.
- The system will cut costs, lower CO₂ emissions and enhance solar energy conversion efficiency for producing chemicals without using fossil fuels.

Figure 40: Press release published on SunCoChem website. See the full text [here](#).

Recent posts

SunCoChem partners met online for their 18M meeting
November 10, 2021

SunCoChem presented during the IWA Odour and Air emissions Conference
October 27, 2021

Presentation of SunCoChem project during the Artificial Photosynthesis Summer School
October 23, 2021

On the other hand, as showed in the following figures, some partners have adapted and published the consortium press release in their corporate webpages.

Recuperarán el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos

Inicio / Ferias, Notas de prensa, Química / Recuperarán el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos

Segueix-nos a les xarxes socials!

Recent

- Innovación que apunta muy alto
marzo 3rd, 2022
- Una nueva plataforma digital con inteligencia artificial permitirá monitorizar la movilidad de las personas y el riesgo de caídas
marzo 1st, 2022
- Presentan en el Mobile World Congress un nuevo sistema que incorpora Inteligencia Artificial y Big Data para optimizar la curación de embutidos
marzo 1st, 2022

Recuperarán el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos

El centro tecnológico Eurecat coordina el proyecto europeo SunCoChem, enmarcado dentro del concepto de **química sostenible**, que desarrollará un reactor para fabricar productos químicos a partir de energías renovables basadas en el dióxido de carbono (CO2) recuperado de la propia industria química y con la ayuda de energía solar, y que ha presentado en el Unprecedented Virtual Forum.

Figure 41: Spanish press release published in the EUT webpage. See the full text [here](#)

Trabaja en Dow Ciencia y Sostenibilidad Sala de Prensa Sedes Contacto

Dow España > Sala de Prensa > Press Releases > Dow participa en el proyecto europeo SunCoChem

Dow participa en el proyecto europeo SunCoChem

Madrid, 6 de octubre de 2020 - Dow Chemical Ibérica ha entrado a formar parte del proyecto europeo SunCoChem, que está financiado por el programa Horizon 2020 de la Unión Europea dentro de la convocatoria CE-NMBP-25-2019 – Photocatalytic synthesis (RIA), coordinado por Eurecat (Centro Tecnológico de Catalunya), y que cuenta con 14 socios de ocho países europeos.

SunCoChem, que comenzó este mes de mayo y se extenderá hasta abril de 2024, aborda la necesidad de la industria química europea de reducir su dependencia de la materia prima de carbono mediante la producción de soluciones integradas y altamente competitivas que permitan la producción de energía y productos químicos de alto valor sin emisiones de carbono. De esta forma, pretende proporcionar una alternativa para producir oxo-químicos sin hacer uso de materias primas derivadas del carbono o petróleo.

Figure 42: Spanish press release published in DOW's webpage. See the full text [here](#)

1.6 Community of Interest

EUT is creating the project's Community of Interest to establish direct dissemination through direct mailing with the objective to increase the impact of our communication and dissemination activities.

The creation of a database of subscribers started at the beginning of the project and will be built during the whole project's execution.

At M10, EUT created a sign-up form to construct and increase the SunCoChem's database. This sign-up form was published on the project's website, as well as shared through the project and partners Social Media channels. Thanks to these actions done, at M23 the SunCoChem's database includes a total of **196 subscribers**.

Additionally, EUT prepared specific messages and different banners to share through SunCoChem and partners' Social Media Channels and promote the sign-up form, helping to increase the total of subscribers.

News and updated and specific information about the project will be distributed periodically via a mailing campaign to ensure that all subscribers to our community are regularly informed about our latest achievements and upcoming events.

The sign-up form complies with GDPR, linking to the project's privacy policy and informing the user about its right to cancel the subscription at any time.

Subscribe now to be updated on SunCoChem project development and latest news on solar-driven chemistry and photoelectrocatalysis

More information - www.suncochem.eu

First Name

Last Name

Email Address

Position

Company

Country

I wish to receive information on:

SunCoChem project developments and activities

Other related projects participated / coordinated by Eurecat

Privacy policy information

SunCoChem will use the information you provide on this form to be in touch with you and to provide updates on project developments and activities.

I have read and I accept the privacy policy

You can unsubscribe at any time by clicking the link in the footer of our emails. For information about our privacy practices, please visit our [privacy policy information on our website](#).

 We use Mailchimp as our marketing platform. By clicking below to subscribe, you acknowledge that your information will be transferred to Mailchimp for processing. [Learn more about Mailchimp's privacy practices here.](#)

Grow your business with mailchimp

Figure 43: Community of Interest sign up form

Figure 44: Example of some banners created to promote the Community of Interest sign up form on social media

1.7 Partners communication activities

SunCoChem partners have also done different types of communication activities with the objective of increasing awareness about the project and disseminating it through an important and large audience.

These activities include, among others: the inclusion of the project's information on partners' website and/or newsletters, the publication of news about SunCoChem on corporate social media channels, or the production of some posters based on project-research to be presented in different events.

See Annex 3.2 to see the complete list of partners' communication activities produced from M1-M23.

The screenshot shows the Eurecat website page for the SunCoChem project. The header includes the Eurecat logo and navigation links. The main content area features a photograph of a scientist in a lab coat using a pipette to transfer liquid into test tubes. Below the photo, the text describes the development of a photoelectrocatalytic tandem reactor (TPER) to manufacture chemical products from renewable energies based on CO₂, water, and sunlight. The project reference is listed as H2020-NMBP-ST-IND-2019 - 862192.

Figure 45: Inclusion of SunCoChem information on Eurecat's website

29/05/2020 NEWS

La nostra ripartenza? E' doppia e punta sulla ricerca

Nei giorni scorsi si sono tenuti i kick-off meeting dei progetti di ricerca SUNCOCHEM e DECADE, due progetti UE H2020 innovativi e di impatto.

Siamo davvero entusiasti di annunciare l'inizio di questi progetti; insieme ai nostri partner svilupperemo soluzioni tecnologiche relative alla chimica verde, in particolare per l'elettroconversione della CO2 in prodotti chimici.

Anche se il lockdown non ci ha fermati, ci piace pensare che SUNCOCHEM e DECADE siano il simbolo della nostra ripartenza, perché la ricerca, in particolare in ambito UE, è un tratto fondamentale del DNA di HYSYTECH.

Figure 46: Inclusion of SunCoChem information on Hysytech's website

15. octubre 2020

First General Meeting of the SunCoChem European Project

On October 23, the first general meeting of the new EU H2020 SunCoChem project will take place.

SunCoChem addresses the need of the EU chemical industry for highly competitive and integrated solutions enabling the carbon-neutral production of high-value chemicals from solar energy, H2O and CO2.

A "tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactor (TPER)" will be developed on a TRL 5 scale; the reactor has an innovative approach thanks to 4 different processes:

1. CO2 selective capture from flue gases or from the atmosphere by permeable membranes and its selective concentration in ILs;
2. photocatalytic water oxidation (anode reaction);
3. photoelectrocatalytic CO2 conversion to CO and H2 (cathode reaction);
4. in-situ CO carbonylation to oxo-products (at cathode surface);

PhotoElectroCatalytic Device for SUN-Driven CO₂ conversion into Green CHEMicals.

Figure 47: Inclusion of SunCoChem information on Laurentia's website

SunCoChem

Sun-driven Chemistry

The SunCoChem project takes an important step in the transition from fossil carbon feedstocks to renewable carbon sources.

Within SunCoChem, Avantium works together with a strong international consortium comprised of universities, technology developers and end-users. SunCoChem is focused on the development of a cutting-edge competitive tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactor (TPER). Renewable energy (sunlight) and a renewable feedstock (CO₂) are combined to create products and materials using multifunctional

SunCoChem has a strong emphasis on industrial applicability. The modular TPER-concept focuses on creating a compact and small system with simplified maintenance that can be integrated in different factory environments at various size scales and productivity targets. The TPER will be validated by converting anthropogenic CO₂ emissions in an industrial environment at the production facility of IFF.

Avantium will take the lead on the development of the CO₂ to glycolic acid-route, which will involve feedstock analysis, process analysis

Figure 48: Inclusion of SunCoChem information on Avantium's website

2. Communication KPIs

The following table shows the current status of the SunCoChem Key performance Indicators (KPIs) established at the beginning of the project to assess the communication activities. As shown in the table, some of these KPIs are already achieved, especially the ones related to the website performance, Twitter activity and visual materials created.

In regards of media relations, once we have relevant results of the project, we will prepare and publish more press releases, increasing SunCoChem's presence in media outlets.

Table 3: Communication KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M23	Target by the end of the project
Website	Number of website visits	Matomo Analytics	4,508	>4,000
	Number of pages viewed		11,771	>15,000
	Number of users		3,298	>2,000
	Average session time		3	>1 min
	Number actions / session		3.2	>1.5
Social Media - Twitter	Twitter: Number of followers	Twitter Analytics	354	>100
	Twitter: Number of tweets		377	>200
	Twitter: Twitter impressions		188,747	>50,000
	Twitter: Likes on tweets		832	>100
	Twitter: Retweets		338	>30
	Twitter: Mentions		118	>20
Social Media – LinkedIn	LinkedIn: Number of followers	LinkedIn Analytics	94	>150
	LinkedIn: Number of posts		25	>50
	LinkedIn: Number of impressions		7,663	>10,000
	LinkedIn: likes/reactions		124	>100
Social Media – YouTube	YouTube: Number of videos uploaded	YouTube Analytics	3	>10
	YouTube: Number of video views		140	>100
Social Media – Partners	Number of posts	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	56	>20
	Number of likes		219	>50
	Number of Shares / Retweets		48	>50
Media Relations	Number of press releases	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	1	>4
	Articles published in media outlets		15	>20
Visual Materials	Number of posters produced		2	>2
	Audiovisual materials		2	12

3. ANNEX

3.1 Articles published in media outlets

Table 4: SunCoChem Media Clipping (M1- M23)

Date	Media	Title	Typology	Link
23/11/2021	Diari Més	Solar, circular i col·laborativa: així serà la química	Print	Link
6/10/2021	ECOticias.com	Medio Ambiente, un potentísimo motor de recuperación en todos los sectores económicos	Online	Link
14/09/2021	Diari de Tarragona	Objetivo: conseguir cero emisiones en 2050	Print	Link
14/09/2021	Diari de Tarragona	Apuesta por la circularidad, sostenibilidad y digitalización de la tecnología química	Print	Link
06/07/2021	InterEmpresas Net	El interés por el medio ambiente, motor de recuperación en todos los sectores económicos	Online	Link
29/03/2021	Diari de Tarragona	Los centros de investigación, la base	Online	Link
26/03/2021	Diari de Tarragona	Los centros de investigación, la base	Print	Link
06/03/2021	Factoria del Futuro	El interés por el medio ambiente, motor de recuperación en todos los sectores económicos	Online	Link
02/01/2021	InterEmpresas Industria Química	La industria química recuperará el CO2 para generar nuevos productos	Print	Link
04/12/2020	Envasprés	Unprecedented Virtual Forum presenta el proyecto SunCoChem	Online	Link
30/11/2020	30Virtual	Eurecat coordina el projecte europeu SunCoChem per recuperar el CO2 de la indústria química per a la generació de nous productes	Online	Link
30/11/2020	Change2Grow (C2G)	Recuperarán el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
29/11/2020	La Vanguardia	La industria química vol utilitzar el seu propi CO2	Print	Link
25/11/2020	Residuos Profesional	El proyecto SunCoChem recuperará el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
24/11/2020	Izaro	El proyecto SunCoChem recuperará el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
23/11/2020	Automatica e instrumentacion	Un proyecto coordinado por Eurecat recupera el CO2 de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
23/11/2020	Retema	El proyecto SunCoChem permitirá recuperar el CO2 en plantas químicas para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
21/11/2020	Factoria del Futuro	Recuperación del CO2 de la industria química para generar nuevos productos	Online	Link
20/11/2020	Revista PQ	Alternativa sostenible a la producción de productos químicos con combustibles fósiles	Online	Link
20/11/2020	El Confidencial Químico	Eurecat presenta el proyecto SunCoChem con la propuesta de una alternativa	Online	Link
20/11/2020	InterEmpresas	La industria química recuperará el CO2 para generar nuevos productos	Online	Link
20/11/2020	El Punt Avui	Recuperar el CO2 de la industria química per fer-ne nous productes	Online	Link
20/11/2020	L'Econòmic	Recuperar el CO2 de la indústria química per fer-ne nous productes	Online	Link

19/11/2020	Buenaquímica.org	Nace un proyecto que recuperará el CO ₂ de la industria química para la generación de nuevos productos	Online	Link
19/11/2020	ABC.es	Eurecat generará nuevos productos a partir del CO ₂ de la industria química	Online	Link
19/11/2020	La Vanguardia	Eurecat generará nuevos productos a partir del CO ₂ de la industria química	Online	Link
10/06/2020	AEQT	DOW participa en el proyecto europeo SunCoChem	Online	Link

3.2 Communication actions carried out by partners

Table 5: Partners communication activities (M1- M23)

Date	Partner	Type of dissemination action	Description	Type of audience	Link
May 2020	EUT	Newsletter	Publication about SunCoChem kick off meeting in the internal newsletter sent to EUT employees	Scientific community	NA
June 2020	HST	Website	Inclusion of SunCoChem information into Hysytech website	General public	Link
July 2020	EUT	Website	Inclusion of SunCoChem information into EUT website	General public	Link
July 2020	EUT	Website	Inclusion of SunCoChem as a highlighted project in the Chemical Unit page	General Public	Link
July 2020	AVANTIUM	Website	Inclusion of SunCoChem information into AVANTIUM website	General public	Link
August 2020	EUT	Newsletter	Publication of SunCoChem's website on the internal newsletter of EUT	Scientific Community	NA
October 2020	IFF	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Internal article about SunCoChem sent to IFF employees	Industrial community	NA
October 2020	DOW	Press release	General press release sent to AEQT (Tarragona chemical cluster)	Industry and scientific community	Link
October 2020	DOW	Press release	Spanish press release published in DOW website	General Public	Link
October 2020	EUT	Newsletter	Publication of the project's first general assembly in the internal newsletter of EUT	Scientific community	NA
November 2020	EUT	Press release	Spanish and Catalan press release published on EUT's website and sent to national and regional media outlets	General Public & Media outlets	Link
November 2020	LAU	Press release	Publication of SunCoChem news on LAU website	General public	Link
November 2020	EUT	Newsletter	Press release of SunCoChem published in the internal EUT's newsletter	Scientific community	NA
April 2021	POLITO, IOLITEC	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication	Production of the poster "Carbon Dioxide Capture and Electrochemical Conversion with Ionic	Industry & scientific community	Link

		(popularised publication)	Liquids” to be presented during the MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit		
April 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Promotion of the first SunCoChem webinar through the internal newsletter of EUT	Scientific community	NA
April 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Short article about the first webinar of SunCoChem published in EUT’s internal newsletter	Scientific community	NA
June 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Short article about the participation of SunCoChem in the EU Green Week published in the internal newsletter of EUT	Scientific community	NA
September 2021	POLITO	Audiovisual materials	Video about the presentation of SunCoChem during the European Researchers’ Night	Scientific and academic community	Link
October 2021	EUT	Newsletter	EUT’s internal newsletter including an article related SunCoChem presentation delivered during the SusChem-España General Assembly	Scientific community	NA
November 2021	HST	Website	Article of SunCoChem on Hysytech website	General public	Link
November 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Publication of the SunCoChem consortium meeting in the internal newsletter of EUT	Scientific community	NA
December 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Publication of the SunCoChem review meeting in the internal newsletter of EUT	Scientific community	NA